

The Blur Building

Reflections on a design for all the senses

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Abstract: The goal of this paper is to illustrate how important and necessary it is for the designer to shift and expand his attention from vision to others senses. In order to do so, it describes the design process of the Blur Building - a cloud whirling above Lake Neuchatel in Yverdon-les-Bains in Switzerland designed by Elizabeth Diller and Ricardo Scofidio. Its main conclusion is that Sensory Design might be an important methodological strategy for heightening and broadening users' experiences, perception, and emotional engagement with the constructed environment.

Key words: *The Blur Building, sensory design, senses, hegemony of vision, Diller Scofidio.*

1. Introduction

The study of people's emotional responses to products, services and environments is still relatively new within design field and has been conducted through various methodological and theoretical approaches.

According to the neuroscientist Antonio Damasio [1], bodily senses give rise to emotions, which in turn provide the basis for rational thought. Based on Damasio's thesis on emotion and its relationship to human activity, we can conclude that our emotional responses to the designed environment are directly related to our senses. Therefore, if designers are to understand people's emotional responses to products and to develop an emotion-focused design process, we need to expand our understanding from vision to the other senses.

In the book *Sensory Design*, authors Joy Monice Malnar and Frank Vodvarka [2] question:

What if we designed for all our senses? Suppose, for a moment, that sound, touch, and odor were treated as equals of sight, and that emotion was as important as cognition. What would our built environment be like if sensory response, sentiment, and memory were critical design factors, more vital even than structure and program?

Designers seem not to be prepared yet to answer this question as our education is highly ‘sight-oriented’, therefore we have been prepared to design a ‘visual’ environment.

Actually, Since Plato and Aristotle, sight had a dominating position over the other senses, as it was usually connected to reason. This hegemony has long influenced certainty and prioritized vision over the other senses. Philosophers such as Descartes believed that sight was the noblest and the universal sense, basing his philosophy on the privilege of vision [2, 3, 4].

Malnar and Vodvarka observe that even with the dominating hegemony of vision in western culture, we count on our five senses to perceive and understand a constructed environment. The editor of the special issue of *Architectural Review* about architecture and sensory experience, Frances Anderton [5], adds that:

We appreciate a place not just by its impact on our visual cortex but by the way in which it sounds, it feels and smells. Some of these sensual experiences elide, for instance our full understanding of wood is often achieved by a perception of its smell, its texture (which can be appreciated by both looking and feeling) and by the way in which it modulates the acoustics of the space.

Malnar and Vodvarka explain that “space is perceived by the visualization of its limits and by kinesthetic experience; i.e. by the sensation of our movements” [2]. So, that means that as vision is added to our movement sensation (kinesthesia), the perception of the environment is even more complete.

The authors also illustrate that the 19th century gardens were designed to surprise and one of the strategies used consisted of not revealing all the vista at once, creating a sense of mystery. The designers used several techniques to retain the attention of the observer. An uneven floor, for example, would force the viewer to tip his head forward about 30° to pay attention to where he was stepping. With this tilting, parts of the brain responsible for stability are on their most sensible position, thus suggesting that uneven floors increase our level of perception of surface. [2]

The authors teach us that smells lend a personality to objects and places that start to be distinguished and are easier to remember and identify. Smells can also trigger an alert state, increasing performance of cognitive tasks, making easier to remember good memories. Sounds can be irritating, gracious, unquiet and frightening [2].

Malnar and Vodvarka observe, however, that other senses apart from vision were forgotten and are not being taken into consideration by designers and architects.

This is where we invite the reader to understand the Blur Building and its history, and challenge your “ordinary sensory interface with the environment and with architecture by putting vision more or less out of the play” [6].

2. World's Fairs and the spectacular future

The Blur Building was a temporary exhibition pavilion built for Expo 2002 in Switzerland by the New York based firm Diller Scofidio. As all World Fairs throughout history, this Expo was not different: it was planned to be a spectacle.

The World's Fair and national expositions are large public exhibitions that started in 1851 in London to show the accomplishments of the works of industry of all nations. Those are spectacles put out by corporate or national entities that present their country's newest technological inventions and realizations. Some important inventions were presented in Worlds' Fairs. The elevator was first presented in 1853 in Dublin, the sewing machine came in 1855 in Paris, the telephone was part of the 1876 innovations in Philadelphia and motion pictures were first exhibited as part of the 1900 World Fair, in Paris.

As architect Elizabeth Diller explains [7]:

The history of world exhibitions is a history of images, spectacles, and conjectures about the future and the role of the sponsoring nation or corporation in forming that future. The pavilion (nation or corporation) capable of articulating a compelling image of the future is understood as a serious contender to inherit that future.

The Crystal Palace, from the First World Fair of 1851, enchanted all visitors by the magnificent new technology of steel and glass, changing completely the experience of space that people had at that time. New spatial experiences were made possible by innovative constructing techniques and notions of interior and exterior start to be mixed up; there were *trees inside* Crystal Palace. The building was disassembled after the World Fair and reassembled years later (possible due to new materials and concept of modularity of structure), thus contributing to a new notion of ephemeral cities and constructions. However, there were some criticisms towards such an astonishing accomplishment. Dostoiévski, for instance, said that people were losing their critical sense towards the Industrial Revolution because of the great enchantment produced by the Palace; a spectacle to the eyes that was a milestone in people's perception of space.¹

Blur Building for Expo 2002 was somehow, like that: "Unlike entering a space with an inside and outside, entering Blur is like stepping into a habitable medium." [7]

Expo 2002 was held in Switzerland at sites in four towns and three lakes. It was planned to encourage "flights of fancy, multicultural encounters and experiences of the senses; (...) punctuated by festivals and events". They wanted it to be a platform for new ideas and new technologies. It was intended to address questions regarding the future, the new millennium and aimed to leave lasting cultural, social and economical remarks. Expo 2002 itself was designed to become a spectacle, "intended not only as a laboratory for ideas but also a great festival of the imagination and emotion". [7]

¹ All information on World Fairs comes from lectures by Professor Dietrich Neumann, Ph.D., on *19th Century Architecture*. Brown University, January to April 2010.

3. Questioning the hegemony of vision: Diller Scofidio (D+S)

D+S is an interdisciplinary studio headed by architects Elizabeth Diller and Ricardo Scofidio, which fuses architecture with media, visual and performing arts. Their main goal, since the beginning, was to ‘reinvent architecture’.

Before having any architectural project ever built, Elizabeth Diller and Ricardo Scofidio started acting in the New York Art scenery and many of their installations questioned, through contemporary lenses, the hegemony of vision. They like ‘blurring genres’, assuming that categories like art, architecture and media are not distinct and can be combined and mixed to create an involving atmosphere. Their designs tend to interrogate spatial conventions of everyday and use “multimedia pieces, installation (site-specific), images and objects that reflect on desire, gender and display; and electronic interventions that blend architecture and media”. This goes against the Cartesian thought of the hegemony of sight as it involves more than merely vision on developing (and appreciating) projects such as these [8].

D+S studio won the Expo 2002 competition and designed the exhibition pavilion at Yverdon-les-Bains together with the multidisciplinary team Extasia, which consisted of landscape architects, exhibition design architects, engineers and logistics managers. The Blur Building was under “the rules of the game ‘The Universe and I, Sensuality and Sexuality’ [and its project should] use seduction and tension to accentuate the power of the senses”, later becoming the symbol of Expo 2002 [3].

4. Designing for all Senses: The design process of the Blur Building

The main premise of the project for the Swiss Expo 2002 exhibition pavilion at Yverdon-les-Bains was that architecture should consist of water, having an absent building; being architecture-free. A hand made sketch on a napkin illustrated in the book *Blur: The Making of Nothing*, describes the idea (Figure 1): “scaleless, formless, massless, colorless, dimensionless, weightless, odorless, centerless, featureless, depthless, meaningless, spaceless, timeless, surfaceless, white-out and white noise” [7].

Figure 1². Hand made sketch on a napkin describing premises of Blur Building.

² All images from this paper, except Figure 2, are from: Diller, E., & Scofidio, R. (2002) *Blur: The Making of Nothing*. New York: Abrams.

Already on the first version of the project presented to the selection committee and the press, there was an intentional white-out produced by the cloud that would deprive the visual sensory stimuli and heighten all other senses. As described by Scofidio: “The density of air inhaled with every breath, the lowered temperature, the delicate and pervasive sound of water spray, and the scent of atomized lake water all engage the senses” [7].

By suppressing vision through the blurring of sight, produced by the cloud effect, Diller and Scofidio planned to employ all other senses. As there was nothing to see in this spectacular cloud, but yet to be *felt*, in the words of Liz Diller: “The Blur Building, undoubtedly a spectacle, puts into question the very convention of spectacle.” [7]

At this point, it seems important to explain that the word ‘spectacle’ comes from the Latin *spectare*, “to see”. Spectacles were an important part of Roman Empire and theaters were very popular and built everywhere at this time in Rome. From the Greek *thea*, “a place of sight” or “the sense of sight”, theater was also a very visual way of entertaining the crowd.³

Liz Diller explains that to ‘blur’ is to make indistinct, to dim, to shroud, to cloud, to make vague, to obfuscate and that *blurred vision* is considered impairment. Being so, blur is equated to loss of our visually obsessed, high-resolution and high-definition culture. She describes the Blur Building as “an immersive environment in which the world is put out of focus so that our visual dependency can be put into focus.” It offers little to see and “provides a rebalancing of the senses” [7].

Scofidio then emphasizes that the Blur Building is an alternative to the convention of the ‘spectacle’. He explains that:

Unlike entering a building, the experience of entering this atmosphere is one in which orientation is lost and time is suspended. We want to exploit the lack of definition characteristic of this atmosphere in order to create an experience of heightened attention to be sustained over a long period. [7]

One of the first versions of the project was inspired by 19th century panoramas, which were cylindrical buildings, with continuous paintings that covered 360 degrees of the interior walls, embracing and surrounding the spectator. The extremely realistic and accurate paintings of towns, battles, conquests and storms were said to transport people into different moments of space and time. In order to immerse the audience in a reliable scenery, people should go into the main room through a dark tunnel, from below and up a staircase under a roof, right in the center of the 360° painting that would be lit from above with natural light, so the moment the spectator got into the circular viewing platform and looked at the picture, one would feel surrounded by that scenery and magically transported to the space and time of the painting. It was a spectacle based on the privilege of sight, as it had no sound, no smell, no texture and no motion.

³ Knowledge obtained from lectures by Rebecca Molholt, Ph.D., on *Spectacles and Entertainments in the Roman World*. Brown University, January to April 2010.

Panoramas were one of the first mass-media phenomena and an example of how art painting could substitute reality, creating simulacra. They were one of the main forms of entertainment at this time, being dethroned only by the early stages of cinema, presented in the 1900 World Fair as ‘cineoramas’.

Panoramas were a silent spectacle for the eye and yet highly influential in 19th century architecture, as it was considered to be an escape from reality, reflecting the search for joy and the desire to immerse oneself in a different environment.⁴ “By wrapping the picture plane around the spectator,” explains Diller, “the panorama integrated actual and illusionistic space.” [7]

One of the first ideas for the exhibition pavilion to be constructed for Expo 2002 at Yverdon-les-Bains was a 21st century technological panorama. It would consist of a dark cylindrical void, on the center of Blur Building, with a circular projection screen, open to the water below, with a suspended platform for 250 viewers at its center. Images would be projected both on the water surface as on the circular screen, with nine projectors organized radially to the screen, involving the viewers with a panoramic image of the on shore town. Webcams would record real time images of local buildings, zooming in and out through open windows of apartments and offices [7]. In these spaces, actors would stage live everyday life, putting again vision into question as it would address the spectator’s voyeuristic aspects.

Figure 2⁵. Panorama comparison: Robert Mitchell, Bakers Panorama at Leicester Square, The British Museum, London (Left) and Blur Building project (Right).

This same version of the project would also have a sushi restaurant immersed in lake water. The idea of having a fish restaurant in the lake, with an aquarium around was another attempt to question the conventions of architecture. The aquarium would be designed to arouse visitors’ interest in local ecology. It would be built of two concentric transparent walls and, in between them; aquatic flora and fauna would be concentrated and monitored. Species present in the lake would be captured in this aquarium which would embrace the sushi restaurant with humor and redundancy; two other strong characteristics of Diller

⁴ All information on Panorama buildings and World Fairs comes from lectures by Professor Dietrich Neumann, Ph.D., on *19th Century Architecture*. Brown University, January to April 2010.

⁵ This image was a creation based on the Bakers Panorama, found in Professor Dietrich Neumann’s lectures and section through the Blur Building project, found in: Diller, E., & Scofidio, R. (2002) *Blur: The Making of Nothing*. New York: Abrams.

Scofidio's projects [7].

Figure 3. Water restaurant at Blur Building.

With major funding cuts and bureaucratic problems within the Expo administration personnel, the idea was not executed and another project had to be designed.

With the abandoning of the panorama and water restaurant project, D+S changed the design radically and came up with a 'led forest' that would interact with each guest. This was a series of scrolling led signs fixed vertically on the structural columns of the building, which would display words or sentences. At first, they were intended to be part of an art installation. However, as the project evolved and a sponsor for the media project was found, D+S started to imagine how could the led signs (needed for safety reasons for one walking through the cloud and not hitting the columns) interact with each visitor.

Figure 4. Led forest.

They understood ‘the cloud as a cleansing bath’ and wanted to rethink ‘spectacle’ tearing vision apart from it. What would a non-visual or blind spectacle be? [7]

D+S together with a team of complementary media professionals, started to design a raincoat that would have a chip installed with the profile of each guest. Once a person was in line, waiting to enter the Blur Building, they would have 20 multiple-choice questions to answer, related to their personal interests. These answers would form a personal profile that would be transferred to the chip in the raincoat. Once one got his raincoat – or ‘braincoat’ as they called – it would have his personal data stored and a computer would deduce his mood and preferences. A tracking device in the coat would locate the person in the pavilion and their mood and interests would be reflected on each led sign, as a secret that was being told to everyone. One would log in on entering the building and log out on exiting. This way, the building would be omniscient [7].

Figure 5. Multiple choice questions

Figure 6. Braincoat

At this point, we invite the reader for a design exercise: how could the braincoat and the cloudy environment created by Diller and Scofidio become a strategy to bring people together for what they have *inside* and not *outside*; for how they *think* and not for how they *look*?

4.1. The final version: using the senses to build social interactions

This was the way the Blur Building apart from involving all senses, also evolved to social interaction. After all, if the building could locate the person and know his/her moods and preference, why not suggest that similar profiles meet? So, with this in mind, D+S thought that a beep could help people move around in a blurred and non sight-oriented space and meet other people. If your profile matched anyone else’s in the building, the two braincoats would start emitting a sound that would be more frequent and quick as the two matches approached. Maybe people could move around and meet through sound, they thought. For that, they also designed a special ‘blush’ mechanism so that the coat would become reddish as it reflected the

matching profiles. Also, the braincoat would be a social leveler as everyone would be dressed in the same way and, with lack of sharp vision, there would be an anonymous intimacy in meeting another person. This would amplify the physical experiences of Blur. As Diller argues [9]:

Is skin not, paradoxically, the most profound thing about us? A border defining within and without, a protective frontier, the envelope of flesh, the body's armor – skin separates and isolates. An interface of pains and pleasures (“erogenous” zones) – skin is both armament and armor. Blushing, blanching, sweating – like the eyes and the mouth, skin is also a medium, a means of communication.

So, finally, media and architecture were coming together as a typical D+S project. However, at last, the braincoat media project was not executed as they lost their main sponsors. Nevertheless, entering a cloud itself was already an experience that would obfuscate vision and question its hegemony and dependence.

So, the last version of the project consisted on a deck on the last floor, called the Angel Deck, and a water bar that sold all waters of the world. The Angel Deck was like stepping on a cloud in the middle of the lake and looking around, to the onshore city. Once again, redundancy (a bar where one could taste water in an environment where there was just water to see, breathe, listen and touch) and metaphor (of being an angel on a cloud) created the typical humor present on D+S's projects. As Guido Incerti summarizes [10]:

D+S has continuously explored blurred information throughout their careers, using media to create a subverted view of architectural space and of the messages generated by it and contained within it. This is a hybrid form of space born out of artistic and technological interference. It is a mode of space constantly mutating, incorporating new media technologies, challenging traditional architectural DNA, scanning the social processes that generated it.

Figures 7, 8 and 9. Angel Deck

In the end, there was nothing to see in the Blur Building: its architecture was almost transparent due to its very light tensegrity structure; it seemed devoted to obscurity. On the other hand, one should paradoxically agree with Reinhold Martin: “There is nothing *but* architecture in the work of D+S; architecture that refuses to hold steady”[11]. We may also add that there was nothing to *see*, but to *feel* in the Blur Building.

Figures 10, 11 and 12. Views of the Blur Building

In this sense, the Blur Building presents itself as an example of what we can call ‘Sensory Design’, as it combines elements such as spatial disorientation, mist, fog, temperature, humidity, wind, weather control and even some mechanisms of social interaction, to heighten other senses than vision. With nothing to be *seen* but *felt*, Blur Building is not just a *spectacle* as described, but an *experience* that engages all senses and may be a new approach to designers that want to expand their attention and design abilities to the emotional reactions of people to products, services, spaces and other built environments.

5. Final considerations: reflections on a design for all senses

The Blur Building’s design process is a lively example of a new design paradigm proposed by Jorge Frascara: the dematerialization of Design.

Exploring a contemporary notion of design, Frascara convokes designers to redefine the objectives of design and its working methods and, above all, not to think about design as a way to create objects, but as a way of people performing their activities, their wills and necessities, from the most basic to the most transcendental. In his own words: “we are no longer seeking universal truths, but an understanding of the plurality and complexity of the issues we have to confront” [12].

We have to stop thinking of design as the construction of graphics, products, services, systems and environments, and think about those as means for people to act, to realize their wishes and satisfy their needs. (...) This requires a better understanding of people, of society and of the ecosystem. [We] need to extend the area of competence of the designer, from knowledge of form, technique, and manufacturing processes, to the understanding of social, psychological, cultural, economic and ecological factors that affect life in society (...). [12]

Jorge Frascara cleverly concludes that “Design is not concerned with objects, but with the impact that those objects have on people” and that any object, being it communicational or physical, “affects the way people operate with other people”. Being so, he suggests a shift of attention by the designers “from the design of objects to the design of situations and activities”. [12]

As Harold Nelson and Erik Stolterman concisely and precisely define [13]:

Design is the ability to imagine that which does not yet exist, to make it appear in concrete form as a new purposeful addition to the real world. Design is the first tradition among the many traditions developed over time including; art, religion, science and technology. We design our cosmologies, our homes, our businesses and our lives.

From what was exposed above, we may conclude that Design is not concerned with objects, but with the *meaningful experiences* that those objects may promote. This means that rather than focusing on products, designers have to focus on the social context in which products will be used and the actions, attitudes, practices, feelings, identity features and social interactions they will promote. This also means that rather than focusing on vision, designers have to focus on putting vision out of the play, in order to heighten and engage all other senses.

We strongly believe that doing so, Sensory Design could be one of the main design strategies for emotional engagement between people and the constructed environment, as it amplifies the perception and interaction that takes place between the two of them. Designing for all the senses might become an important methodological approach for the shift of attention from the *design of objects* to the *design of situations and activities* to occur, as proposed by Jorge Frascara.

We may finally conclude that designing for all the senses can also be an important step towards designing for and with humor, solidarity, cooperation, compassion, diversity, responsibility, social consciousness, justice and other important forms of living in a more brotherly and sensitive society.

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